

PROTECTION OF LAND RESOURCES AND WISE USE

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ABSTRACT

this article is devoted to the conservation and rational use of land resources.

KEY WORDS

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Soil salinization, erosion, desertification and its negative consequences. In nature, soil erosion or erosion is observed under the influence of wind and water. But today, due to the wrong attitude of people to the soil, that is, the wrong plowing of steep lands, over-irrigation, the wrong attitude to plants, re-salinization, application of toxic chemicals, etc. cause soil erosion. Anthropogenic erosion is a consequence of the misuse of soil resources, the main causes of which are deforestation and deforestation, non-compliance with the norm of grazing livestock in pastures, the use of improper methods of farming, and others. It is estimated that 3,500 hectares of fertile soil are lost every day as a result of erosion on Earth. Water erosion has taken more mountainous, and in mountainous areas, wind erosion is observed.

Prevention of erosion processes includes restoration of vegetation cover, proper implementation of agro-technical measures, construction of green protective shields, scheduled hydrotechnical measures, etc.

The crop rotation method was criticized in the sixties and banned for many years. Later, in many regions, due to monoculture, it was not possible to widely introduce crop rotation. As a result, the fertility of the land gradually decreased.

The total area of agricultural land in the country is 28 million hectares, including 23 million hectares of pastures, 0.7 million hectares of arable land and 4.2 million hectares of irrigated land.

Cotton is grown on 42% of irrigated lands and grain on 12%

In the past, the fields were much smaller and surrounded by thick fruit trees. These trees protected the soil from strong

winds. The trees also served a biological drainage function, i.e., they pumped groundwater through the roots, preventing it from rising to the top of the soil, helping to prevent soil erosion and salinization

During the years of stagnation, the fruit trees around the farm lands were uprooted and the crops were expanded, increased erosion. This happened in many areas of Kashkadarya region, such as Nishan, Chirakchi, Kamashi, Mubarek, Mirishkor.

In recent years, the use of chemicals in agriculture has become more widespread, but in 1993 in Nishan, Dehkanabad, Kamashi, Kasan districts of the region were added 12 tons of highly toxic substances against macrococci, such as 12 tons of hexachlorane, 1.5 tons of chlorophos, 2 tons of BI-58. Ilanildi.

These toxins, which have accumulated in the ground, are pushed through the roots of the plant and accumulated in its fruits, passing through the weeds into the animal's body and poisoning it. Water, which contains several times more toxic chemicals than normal, can lead to diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, liver, respiratory system, nervous system, colds, allergies, oncology, etc. 'p were exposed.

Chemical toxins from food damage the body's immune system

Measures to protect land resources. Our goal is to make our people physically and mentally healthy. To do this, we must first rid our land of various toxic chemicals and make it healthy. Only then can we provide people with quality, nutritious food. According to experts, the removal of accumulated toxic waste from the soil should be achieved through the widespread use of crop rotation and other

biological methods for 8-10 years without the use of any drugs

I.A Karimov's book "Uzbekistan on the threshold of the XXI century" provides the following information about the land. At the same time, the land is not only a great wealth, but also a factor that determines the future of our country. This is especially evident in Uzbekistan. Because the economic and demographic function of the land is growing from year to year. Only 7.8% of the total land area of the country, which is more than 448.9 thousand square kilometers, is arable land.

Until recently (1990), cotton accounted for almost 75% of the arable land. No other country in the world has had such a high cotton monopoly. This has led to the weakening of the soil, soil fertility, deterioration of its water-physical properties, soil suffocation and increased erosion processes.

Therefore, the most important task in nature protection in Uzbekistan is to improve the condition of the land, to take measures to reduce soil pollution.

Article 55 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Land, including soil, is a national wealth, like other natural resources, which must be used wisely and is under state protection." According to Article 16 of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on April 30, 1998, it is state property. In recent years, the reduction of cotton fields, the wider introduction of crop rotation, the normalization of the use of mineral fertilizers and other measures have led to an improvement in soil conditions.

Every self-respecting country, independent and sovereign state strives to regulate any social relations by law. Soil is no exception. Because the soil is so

important in human life, it will always be the object of social relations, that is, the compromise that occurs between people of

property, economic, political, educational, cultural, ecological and sociological nature.

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